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ABSTRACTS

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Development of lipid polymer nanoparticles as the rapapeutics for Alzheimer's Disease

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Abstract: Alzheimer's disease is a prevalent and devastating neurodegenerative disorder that affects millions of people worldwide. As populations age, the incidence of Alzheimer's is expected to rise, making it a significant public health concern. Effective treatments or interventions can significantly improve the quality of life for affected individuals and alleviate the burden on healthcare systems. This research project represents a multidisciplinary effort to advance the field of Alzheimer's disease treatment by leveraging Technological Solutions for innovative lipid polymer nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery. The primary objective is to develop a platform for encapsulating and delivering therapeutic agents to target specific regions within the brain, thus enhancing treatment efficacy. Tailored nanoparticles and drug delivery mechanisms can enhance the precision and efficacy of treatments while minimizing side effects. As a potential extension, the scope of the project includes the exploration of preclinical studies using animal models of Alzheimer's disease. This allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the therapeutic potential of the developed lipid polymer nanoparticles in a more physiological context, providing valuable insights into their efficacy and safety. The outcomes of this study have the potential to significantly contribute to the development of novel therapeutic strategies for combating Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, neurodegenerative disorder, lipid polymer nanoparticles, drug delivery.

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